

CHALLENGES IN DESIGNING SUSTAINABLE PAPER PACKAGING FROM INVASIVE PLANTS

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Original scientific paper

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10007366

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Abstract: *Consumer goods are usually enclosed in protective packaging to protect them from vibration and impact shocks during handling and transportation. Bio-degradable materials such as moulded pulp and honeycomb paper panels have emerged as formidable and sustainable alternatives to EPS. These materials exhibit distinct nonlinear and orthotropic behaviour and can be characterized by a relatively high stiffness. These makes them far from being regarded as an ideal cushioning material. Due to the inferior paper-based packaging performance, the improvement of protective and cushioning properties relay on the structural optimization of the packaging design. With proper design in terms of minimizing the vibration transfer path to the product itself and by avoiding extensive plastic deformation it is possible to significantly enhance cushioning performance of paper-based packaging even at multiple impacts. This requires advanced numerical models using finite element models using a highly nonlinear material models. This article presents the process of creating a numerical model for samples made from paper pulp, which also incorporate fibres from invasive plants, and introduces the method to identify its material properties. Leveraging this strategy enables to predict the static and cushioning characteristics of the pulp using numerical simulations.*

Keywords: paper pulp, numerical simulation, lignocellulosic material, packaging, finite element model

1 INTRODUCTION

Commercial goods are commonly encased in protective-packaging buffers to protect them from damage due to vibration and impact shock during handling and transportation (Kun et al., 2017). The materials used to fabricate protective packaging are usually plastic foam, such as EPS, with good cushioning performance and cost effectiveness, but they are not friendly to the environment (Andena et al., 2018). To prevent impact-induced damage to a product, a reliability test has traditionally been carried out using the “design-prototype-test-redesign” approach, which can be expensive, tedious and time consuming (Lye et al., 2004). More advanced approaches rely on a numerical, static structural analysis of the packaging in connection with an experimentally obtained material cushioning curve to determine the optimum contact area and thus achieve the best cushioning performance (Sanchez et al., 2019; Ozturk et al., 2011).

Figure 1. Replacement of EPS with paper based packaging solutions.

However, for sustainability reasons, expressed as renewability and recyclability, biodegradable alternatives such as paper-based packaging are being introduced (Lye, 2004) (Figure 1). In the home-appliance packaging industry, corrugated and honeycomb paperboard materials have been widely used for the packaging of lightweight household appliances (Kun et al., 2017; Fadiji et al., 2018). A lot of research has been carried out to quantify the cushioning properties of packaging materials such as moulded pulp using an aqueous slurry of cellulosic fibres (Hua et al., 2020). The packaging industry, being a significant contributor to

environmental degradation, has identified the need for transition towards more sustainable production (Čepon et al., 2021). Leveraging invasive plants in the production of paper packaging presents a novel approach to address both environmental concerns and the issue of invasive species. However, this approach is not without its challenges. Due to the inferior performance of paper-based packaging that incorporates invasive species, enhancing its protective and cushioning features necessitates a numerical structural optimization of the packaging design. From this perspective and taking into account the intricate behaviour of paper material, it becomes challenging to rely on traditional packaging design methodologies through trial and error. Instead, structural optimization should leverage advanced modeling strategies, such as finite element methods.

This structural optimization is usually based on coupled dynamics simulations of the packaging, together with the product. Recent advances of the finite-element method (FEM) have further promoted the development of a detailed modeling packaging dynamics response. The major challenges to be coped with are the multi-physic, multi-scale and nonlinear nature of the paper and the complex geometry of the packaging design that results in huge models and long computational times.

In this paper, we introduce a modeling strategy based on the experimental characterization of deformation curve and Finite Element Method (FEM) for determining the material properties and performance, as well as delineating the cushioning curves for moulded pulp that incorporates invasive plants. These standard methods provide us general guidance for the evaluation of cushioning performance of pulp with inclusion of invasive plants fibres.

2 PAPER PULP MATERIAL MODEL

Utilizing a bi-kinematic hardening material model in paper modeling is crucial to accurately predict the paper's behavior under various mechanical loadings. This approach integrates both isotropic and kinematic hardening, hence offering a detailed insight into the evolution of the material's yield surface during the deformation process. This model combines two distinct hardening mechanisms: isotropic hardening and kinematic hardening, to provide a more comprehensive description of a material's behavior under cyclic loading conditions (Figure 2). In the context of this model:

Isotropic Hardening: This aspect considers the uniform expansion of the yield surface in the stress space. Essentially, it portrays how a material hardens

uniformly when exposed to plastic deformation, leading to an increase in yield stress.

Kinematic Hardening: This aspect focuses on the translation of the yield surface in the stress space, depicting the alignment of the material's internal structure as it undergoes deformation. It helps in describing phenomena such as the Bauschinger effect, where a material exhibits different yield stresses under reversed loading due to the translation of the yield surface.

Figure 2. Isotropic and kinematic hardening.

This type of material model was successfully applied in this paper to determine the mechanical behaviours of paper pulp under different forces and deformations. Paper pulp, which primarily comprises of cellulose fibers, is a complex material whose characteristics are markedly non-linear, anisotropic, and viscoelastic. At the macroscopic scale, the paper pulp is considered as a continuum, where the focus is primarily on its bulk properties. The modeling here takes into account the overall response of the paper pulp to external forces, including its elastic, plastic, and viscous behaviours. Using bi-kinematic hardening material model, it is possible to model and anticipate how the pulp material will behave during mechanical loads, taking into consideration factors like density, fibre orientation, and moisture content, which significantly affect the pulp's mechanical characteristics.

3 EXPERIMENTAL IDENTIFICATION OF FORCE-DEFORMATION CURVE

Experimental characterization of deformation curve was conducted on sample pulp cubs with two configuration:

- Configuration 1 – Raw pulp
- Configuration 2 – Raw pulp with 20% of Japanese knotweed

In the Figure 3 the samples of pulp pots are presented that were produced using the 3D printed moulds.

Figure 3. Pulp pots produced using printed mould.

The purpose of the first experimental part was to conduct a compression test of the sample pots for both analysed configurations with to determine pot material properties. The pot was placed between the jaws of a tensile-compression device and then measured the reaction force on the upper jaw versus displacement of the jaws. For a more detailed demonstration, Figure 4 below showcases one of the samples in both undeformed and deformed states.

Figure 4. Pulp pot static compression test: a) undeformed configuration, b) deformed configuration.

During a compression test, the applied force and the resulting deformation are analysed to indirectly determine the material's mechanical properties. Initially, in the elastic region, the material undergoes reversible deformation, where it can return to its original form once the force is removed. As the force increases, the material enters the plastic region, where the deformation becomes permanent. Understanding this force-deformation relationship is vital as it helps in predicting

how the pulp material would behave under various stress conditions. It is essential to note that the specific force-deformation characteristics can vary based on the intrinsic properties of the pulp material, including its density, fibre orientation, and moisture content.

As is can be seen from Figure 5, incorporating shorter fibres of Japanese knotweed into the pulp material results in only slightly worsen material properties. This suggests a justification for using Japanese knotweed in the pulp.

Figure 5. Force-deformation curve for pulp pots.

4 NUMERICAL MODEL AND IDENTIFICATION OF PULP MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The development of numerical model began with the CAD model of analysed pots. The CAD model of the pot is presented in Figure 6a and the corresponding FEM model is presented in Figure 6b. The elements used in numerical simulation where shell elements in order to improve the computational efficiency and convergence of numerical model.

Figure 6. Numerical model of pulp cup; a) CAD model, b) FEM model.

Material properties of pulp was determined by updating the numerical model with real-time data obtained from actual pulp force-deformation measurement (Figure 5). This iterative process, which integrates experimental data into the computational framework, allows for a more precise and reliable prediction of the pulp's performance in various applications. Based on this optimization process finally the material parameters of pulp material where deduced as indicated in the table 1.

Table 1. Identified material parameters of bi-kinemeatic hardening material model for raw pulp.

Parameter	Value	Unit
<i>density</i>	<i>650.1</i>	<i>MPa</i>
<i>Young modulus</i>	<i>50.5</i>	<i>MPa</i>
<i>Poisson ratio</i>	<i>0.01</i>	
<i>resistance to compression</i>	<i>1.72*10⁷</i>	<i>Pa</i>
<i>Shear modulus</i>	<i>2.5*10⁷</i>	<i>Pa</i>
<i>Yield strength</i>	<i>0.075</i>	<i>MPa</i>
<i>Tangent modulus</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>MPa</i>

The correlation between the deformation data from the numerical model and the results obtained from experimental observations at various load stages are presented in Figure 7. By adopting the identified material parameters defined in Table 1 a high degree of correlation between the simulated and experimentally obtained behaviour can observed. In addition, the numerically predicted and experimentally obtained deformation-force curve are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Comparison of deformation shape between the numerical model and actual experiment of paper pulp samples.

Figure 8. Comparison of numerically and experimentally obtained force-deformation curve for pulp pots.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced a strategy for simulating paper pulp structures utilizing a bi-kinematic hardening material model. Our findings indicate a comparable mechanical performance between pure pulp and pulp composed of a 20% incorporation of Japanese knotweed, thereby justifying the use of invasive plant materials in pulp production. Leveraging numerical models together with an iterative process enabled accurate identification of pulp material properties. This methodology offers a significant potential to numerically predict packaging deformations under static and dynamic loads that encoures during transportation.

Acknowledgments: *The authors acknowledge financial support from the Ministry of Cohesion and Regional Development of the Republic of Slovenia, provided under the Norway grants, according to grant agreement No. C1541-22B710043 (LEAP project).*

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